

Emotional cartography in design: A novel technique to represent emotional states altered by spaces

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Abstract Bio-signals as evaluation methods have been increasingly used for design and architectural research over the last few years. Understanding how environmental factors influence people's emotions by using psychophysiological tools represents an opportunity to improve design processes. As a part of an extensive exploration toward emotional maps, EDA signals were used. This preliminary work presents a study in which 12 participants explored an Immersive Virtual Environment (IVE) using a Head-Mounted Display while their sympathetic reaction was being registered. The response to the IVE (3 rooms designed to evoke neutrality, stress and calm states) was measured using both phasic electrodermal activity data gathered during IVE's exploration and psychometric response collected by post-questionnaire. Results show that the IVE evoked the expected emotional states to be measured, EDA-phasic was an appropriate tool to measure emotional states and the "emotional map" created by superimposing an emotional heatmap on the architectural layout confirms that it is possible to represent emotional states altered by spaces graphically.

Keywords *Emotional map, EDA, Virtual reality, Sympathetic reaction*

Introduction

Recently, researchers oriented to design and architecture have employed different psychophysiological signals in order to measure affective experience during simulated product interactions (Jenkins, Brown, & Rutterford, 2009; Laparra-Hernández et al, 2009). Numerous studies based on engineering approaches to automatically recognize emotions from physiological responses have been published (Goshvarpour, Abbasi & Goshvarpour, 2015). In all of them, the dataset was comprised of a set of features extracted from peripheral signals, such as electrocardiogram (ECG), galvanic skin response (GSR), electromyography (EMG) and others (Demangeot & Broderick, 2010). Design and architecture have started to use these physiological measures in product evaluations, in respect of the demanding need to generate mixed methodologies (Monestina et al, 2014).

This study focuses on the capacity of GSR signal to detect emotional states and the possibility to plot it. Emotional cartography (or emotional maps) is not a novel concept. This was popularized by Christian Nold

(2009). Environments affect people at cognitive and emotional levels. The idea of an emotional map is to place and plot these emotions elicited by spaces. Designers and architects have explored this concept before, developing different strategies to map the relation between places and emotions (Litteman, 2012; Fischer et al, 2014; Amilant-Szary and Mekjajian, 2015). However, Emotional Cartography remains a challenge because of the emotional characterization and tenuous relation with maps.

GSR is a bio-signal obtained by skin response which is also known as electrodermal activity (EDA). This signal refers to the variation of the electrical properties of the skin in response to sweat secretion. By applying a low constant voltage, the change in skin conductance (SC) can be measured non-invasively (Benedek & Kaernbach, 2010). EDA signals are related with the sympathetic nervous system. EDA has been used for more than a century as an indirect measurement of response to stimuli (CarretiéArangüena, 2011) since it is a signal which is rather easy to gather and understand, and the literature suggest that responds

Figure 1. Virtual Environments used in the study.

to threatening stimuli, as a reflection of arousal activity related with emotional states, and being the amplitude of the electrodermal response proportional to the “emotionality” of the eliciting stimuli (Fowles, 1980; Boucsein, 2012). It has already been used as a tool to assess environments, like Parson et al. (1998) who used it to evaluate differences in stress recovery between natural and urban environments, or to design elements such as colors (Jacobs and Hustmyer, 1974) and floorings (Laparra-Hernández et al, 2009). As Immersive Virtual Environments (IVE) have proved their ability to replicate real scenarios and the evoked emotional states (Rojas et al, 2015; Rodríguez et al, 2015), and have been previously used for EDA measurement (Felnhofer et al, 2015), an IVE was used to present the stimuli.

Materials and methods

Participants and apparatus

This study was conducted with 12 participants (4 female, 8 male) with ages ranging from 27 to 46 (M: 33.25; SD: 4.95) who did not receive any compensation for it. All participants reported normal or corrected vision, no heart rate problems and being familiar with VR systems.

The device used to acquire the EDA signal was a portable physiological wristband (E4 by Empatica©, www.empatica.com). EDA data was sampled at 4Hz (0.001 to 100 μ Siemens). To display VR environments, high immersive head mounted displays (HDM) were employed (Oculus DK2, www.oculus.com). This Head-Mounted Display (HMD) is 7-inches wide with 1920x1080 pixels resolution split between both eyes, yielding 960x1080 pixels per eye. Sennheiser HD215 headphones were also used with a frequency response of 12 - 22000 Hz. The computer which was used to run all software has a core i5 (3.4 GHz) CPU with 8GB of RAM, and a graphical-card AMD RADEON r9-255 Series GPU (2 GB). A gamepad was used for user navigation.

Stimuli

The IVE was made using SketchUp® (v2016) and exported to graphical development platform using Unity 3D® (v5.3) for displaying in Oculus DK2. The designed environment contained 28.834 polygons and 25 textures. It consisted of five rooms; two as entry and exit points and the ones between them were designed to evoke three emotional states: Neutrality, Stress and Calm (see Figure 1). Both stress and calm rooms were designed following evidence-based guidelines to achieve the required emotional states: the level of enclosure and outside views (Chang, 2005), ceiling height (Meyers-Levy, & Zhu, 2007), sharp or curved contours (Vartanian et al, 2013) and gaudy (red, black) or soft colors (blue, lilac) (Yildirim et al, 2011; Jalil et al, 2012). Sound factors were included to increase emotional states inside rooms; traffic and mechanical sounds in stress room and nature sounds in the calm room were added (Alvarsson, Wiens, & Nilsson, 2010; Valenti et al, 2012). Due to the VR tendency to increase stress levels (Mon Williams, Warm, & Rushton, 1993), the calm room was placed at the end of the path.

Procedure

The participants were asked to sit in front of a computer with a gamepad, headphones and the HMD at dimly-lit laboratory room. The instructions were given while participants were putting these devices and the E4 wristband on. Before starting the task, a baseline was conducted to equalize participants to a similar emotional state. The main task designed for this study was a free exploration through the rooms with no time limit. The participants started the exploration in the entry point before walking to the neutral room. The task ends when participants cross the calm room to the exit point (see Figure 2). The participants' movements in IVE were tracked by a script running under the graphical development platform, in order to export position and time references into a data base. A post-questionnaire with basic demographic questions and 7-point Likert-scales about emotional state from Russell, Weiss, & Mendelsohn (1989) was fulfilled. Three questions were

Figure 2. Top view of the complete VR environment.

asked to rate the levels of pleasure, arousal and stress. The scales used have a double purpose: to validate the designed environments (neutral, stressful, and relaxing spaces) and to find possible correlations between psychometric response and EDA bio-signal.

Data analysis and results

The registered EDA signal was pre-processed and analyzed with an EDA analysis toolbox (Ledalab® V3.4.8, www.ledalab.de) running under Matlab 2012a. Pre-processing consisted of a visual diagnostic of artefacts and their corrections. A continuous decomposition analysis (CDA, Benedek and Kaernbach, 2010) was used to clean the signal and to detect a phasic component associated to ambient discrete stimuli caused by abrupt increases in skin conduction (Dawson, 2001). The phasic signal of every subject was exported and synchronized in a temporal line. Once the EDA-phasic signal was ready, both data bases (EDA-phasic, and the position registered by script), were introduced to Matlab script to synchronize and create a heat map representation.

To control inter-subject variations, EDA-phasic data was unitarized between 0 and 1 for each subject using 0 as the lowest score and 1 as the highest score for sympathetic activation. In order to ensure the quality of the representation, we considered the following assumptions: 1) if participants crossed the same point in space, the maximum EDA-phasic data would be taken between points (individual maps were made to corroborate the data); and 2) after analysing all the subjects, an overall heat map was made by plotting sympathetic activation means only if, at least, 25% of the sample (three participants) crossed the same point in the space.

The heat map representation is shown in Figure 3. It should be clarified that this kind of heat map represents the highest unitary EDA in red colour and the lowest data in blue colour. However, in this

representation the blank space does not represent low data for sympathetic activation, but rather that data level activation is unknown because it does not comply with the two previous considerations. The results of unitary EDA means and data obtained from questionnaire show in Table 1.

A descriptive analysis is shown in Table 1. Psychometric and EDA data was treated with Z-standardized means to simplify comparative interpretation.

Shapiro-Wilk Test revealed that the distributions were not normal. Kruskal-Wallis Test found significant differences between stress and calm rooms both in questionnaire and EDA responses (Pleasure $p=0.000$, Arousal $p=0.000$, Stress $p=0.000$ and EDA-phasic $p=0.033$) and no significant differences neither between neutral and relax rooms nor between neutral and stress rooms. Spearman's Rho Test was used to find out bivariate correlations within variables, showing statistically significant inverse correlation between EDA-Pleasure (coef=-0.379 $p=0.023$) and non-significant correlation between EDA-Arousal (coef=0.169 $p=0.235$) and EDA-Stress (coef=0.221 $p=0.195$).

Table 1. Statistics descriptive of rooms' perception and EDA data.

Room	Pleasure	Arousal	Stress	EDA unitarized
	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)
Neutral	0.25 (0.54)	-0.33 (0.71)	-0.67 (0.56)	-0.025 (1.280)
Stress	-1.18 (0.39)	0.98 (0.73)	1.16 (0.53)	0.533 (0.809)
Calm	0.93 (0.47)	-0.64 (0.73)	-0.49 (0.62)	-0.508 (0.546)

Figure 3. Emotional map: red color shows the highest unitary EDA score and blue color, the lowest.

Discussion

In this study, different spaces, evidence-based designed, achieved to elicit the expected emotional responses in the participants, as the questionnaire endorses. Subsequently, recording psychophysiological response while tracking spatial location throughout the IVE was possible. The signal could be processed to obtain solid data and statistical analysis found significant differences in psychophysiological responses between stress and calm rooms highlighting an inverse correlation between EDA signal and pleasure.

Electrodermal activity seems to be adequate to create emotional representations in correlation to the pleasure generated by space (Kreibig, 2010) contributing to previous emotional cartography research charted by Nord (2009), Littenan (2012), Fischer et al (2014) or Amilant-Szary & Mekjajian (2015).

This is a preliminary study with a reduced sample size in order to obtain experience in conducting a future study with a larger sample size and better analysis methods. EDA data showed substantially different measurements between participants (magnitude order) that requires normalized statistics for comparison. A criterion must be considered to select the minimum number of participants to represent in a map.

Psychophysiological environment effects were marked by individual perception of participants and the creative criteria of the designer. This study included multiple variables (color, geometry, heights, decorations and sounds) to guarantee sympathetic activation. A disadvantage can be created to ignore the

whole influence of one of each of these aesthetic elements in the environment. Nevertheless, this is not the aim of this study.

Conclusion

The EDA signal has potential to be considered as an essential psychological tool to quantify emotional states inside environments and the development of emotional cartographic. This study exposed a novel technique to represent emotional states. The proposal of our technique is to help and promote the objective quantification of subjective experiences and locate the point where this occurs. Future studies aim to bring the results further by using other psychophysiological signals like ECG. Being able to easily plot emotional states in architectural layouts opens a range of possibilities: evaluating the isolated impact of design elements in mood (color, vegetation...), assessing existing places for critical points or designing task-oriented spaces (e.g. relaxation, creativity...). That is, designing better places.

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